

Antibacterial Biomaterials through Synergy of Metallic Ions-Substituted Calcium Phosphates and Bacteriophages No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/056 (1.1.1.9/1/24/I/001)

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/056 "Antibacterial Biomaterials through Synergy of Metallic Ions-Substituted Calcium Phosphates and Bacteriophages" 01.07.2025-30.06.2028.

This project generates interdisciplinary data spanning materials science, microbiology, and cell biology, produced during the synthesis, characterization, and biological evaluation of ion-substituted and bacteriophage-functionalized calcium phosphate (CaP) biomaterials. The data will support the project's fundamental objectives, specifically the development of antimicrobial and biocompatible CaP biomaterials.

Data Types: experimental parameters from synthesis (*e.g.*, pH, temperature, concentrations, ion ratios); characterization data - XRD (phase composition), FTIR/Raman (molecular structure), SEM (morphology), ICP-MS (chemical analysis), TGA/DSC (thermal behavior), N₂ sorption (surface area), ion release profiles in physiological/inflammatory conditions (via ICP-MS); biological assay data - MIC values (microdilution method), cytotoxicity; microbiological data - bacteriophage titers, plaque assay results, phage adsorption efficiency, bacterial viability (optical density).

Documentation: protocols, raw data, processed data, etc.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Antibacterial Biomaterials
through Synergy of Metallic
Ions-Substituted Calcium
Phosphates and
Bacteriophages
(1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/056)

Researchers

Liga Stipniece (0000-0001-5472-7684)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Antibacterial Biomaterials through Synergy of Metallic Ions-Substituted Calcium Phosphates and Bacteriophages No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/056 (1.1.1.9/1/24/I/001)

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Contact: [Stipniece Liga \(liga.stipniece@rtu.lv\)](mailto:liga.stipniece@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: Antibacterial Biomaterials through Synergy of Metallic Ions-Substituted Calcium Phosphates and Bacteriophages (1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/056)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-SA-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-08-13

4. Templates

Descriptions

Optical Density at 600 nm Measurements for Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of Metal (Cu, Ga, Zn) Ion Solutions

The optical density (OD) at 600 nm is measured for bacterial cultures incubated with varying concentrations of metallic ion solutions. This wavelength is chosen because it provides a reliable estimate of cell density in bacterial suspensions without significant interference from most growth media. By comparing OD₆₀₀ values of treated cultures to untreated controls, the degree of bacterial growth inhibition at each metal concentration can be quantified.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To monitor bacterial growth in the presence of different concentrations of metallic ions and determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) - the lowest concentration at which visible bacterial growth is inhibited. OD₆₀₀ measurements serve as a proxy for cell density, allowing rapid, non-destructive assessment of antimicrobial activity.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

150

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Data were not re-used in order to ensure full control over experimental design, maintain reproducibility, and allow for accurate interpretation of results.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data in this dataset might be useful to other researchers, e.g., microbiologists - researchers studying antimicrobial properties of metals against bacteria and developing new strategies to combat antibiotic-resistant strains; material scientists - developers of antimicrobial biomaterials, or packaging incorporating metallic ions.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata will include measurement parameters of the data included in the dataset described in readme.txt text file.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

This dataset is under restricted access to protect ongoing analyses and potential intellectual property.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are under embargo to allow completion of ongoing analyses and publication of additional findings.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo offers a secure, flexible, and widely accepted platform for sharing and preserving research data, making it an excellent choice for researchers seeking to manage access to their datasets effectively.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The datasets generated in this study are provided in XLS format. They can be accessed and analyzed using Microsoft Excel, LibreOffice, or Google Sheets for general viewing and editing.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected data formats are XLS. The datasets provided in XLS format are compatible with a wide range of both proprietary and open-source software. They can be opened and manipulated using Microsoft Excel, LibreOffice, and OpenOffice. Additionally, the data can be exported to standard formats such as CSV or TSV, which are fully interoperable with virtually all statistical and data visualization software, facilitating integration and recombination with other datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Physicochemical characterization of non-, Cu-, Zn-, and Ga-substituted calcium phosphates

The datasets comprises a comprehensive set of measurements describing the structural, morphological, compositional, and surface-related properties of calcium phosphate materials in their pure (non-substituted) form, as well as those substituted with copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), and gallium (Ga) ions.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This type of data is generated to link ion substitution with measurable material properties, enabling the rational design of calcium phosphate-based biomaterials with enhanced and predictable biological performance.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG

- XLS

- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Although prior studies exist on substituted calcium phosphates, we generated new data because experimental conditions, substitution levels, and material properties can vary significantly between studies. Factors such as synthesis method, ion concentration, calcination temperature, pH, and aging time strongly influence the crystallinity, particle size, surface chemistry, and bioactivity of calcium phosphates.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

These data provide a reference framework for anyone developing, optimizing, regulating, or studying calcium phosphate-based biomaterials, particularly for bone repair, dental, or antimicrobial applications.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

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Yes

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2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

No special tools, generally available software capable of opening data file formats mentioned in 1.1.3.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected data formats are XML, TXT, PDF, CSV, XLS, TIFF, PNG.

These data formats can be open using following softwares:

1. XML - VS Code, Notepad++
2. TXT - Notepad, VS Code
3. PDF - Adobe Acrobat Reader, Foxit Reader
4. CSV - Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets
5. XLS / XLSX - Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets

6. TIFF - Adobe Photoshop, GIMP

7. PNG - Adobe Photoshop, GIMP

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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